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Evaluation of the Implementation of International Ship and Port Facility Security Code for Maritime Security Governance in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed the implementation of the International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code and maritime security governance in Nigeria's Gulf of Guinea (GoG) region. The GoG remains a global hotspot for piracy, kidnapping, illegal oil bunkering, and attacks on offshore installations. The research investigates if the ISPS Code has achieved measurable reductions in maritime insecurity by comparing pre- and post-implementation trends of piracy incidents. The study employs the incidence rate model to evaluate variations in attacks against ships between 2006 and 2020. Findings reveal persistent insecurity, weak institutional capacity, and uneven ISPS compliance across the GoG. Challenges include inadequate infrastructure, poor inter-agency coordination, insufficient training of security personnel and lack of harmonized legal frameworks. Moreover, governance deficits, corruption, and limited funding undermine the effectiveness of maritime security initiatives despite regional cooperation efforts under the Yaoundé Code of Conduct. The study emphasizes that the ISPS Code's effectiveness depends on national and regional governance structures, stakeholder collaboration, and sustained investment in maritime domain awareness systems. Policy recommendations include strengthening legal harmonization among GoG states, improving inter-agency coordination, enhancing surveillance and intelligence-sharing networks, and increasing investments in port security infrastructure and personnel training. By integrating ISPS implementation with broader governance reforms, Nigeria and its regional partners can improve maritime safety, foster investor confidence, and promote sustainable blue economy growth within the Gulf of Guinea.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

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The Gulf of Guinea (GoG), the tropical Atlantic seaboard extending from the West and Central African region, covering Nigeria up to Senegal and Angola — is one of the world's most important and contested littoral regions. It carries a large share of West and Central Africa's seaborne trade, hosts major hydrocarbon extraction and export operations, and supports vital fisheries and coastal livelihoods. At the same time the region has become a global hotspot for maritime crime: piracy, armed robbery at sea, kidnappings for ransom, illicit oil bunkering, vandalism of oil and gas infrastructure and trafficking, and illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing have imposed severe economic, human-security and governance costs on coastal states and the international shipping community. Recent reporting shows that while recorded incidents in the GoG fell from the peak years around 2020, crew kidnappings and the vulnerability of ships and port facilities remain a persistent threat (IMO, 2023; IMB, 2023, IMB, 2024).

The International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code — adopted under SOLAS Chapter XI-2 and made mandatory in 2004 — provides the primary international legal and technical framework for preventing and responding to threats against ships and port facilities. Nigeria as a dominant player in the GoG maritime domain commenced the full implementation of the ISPS code in the year 2007. The ISPS Code prescribes responsibilities for contracting governments, port authorities, ship operators and security officers; it sets out risk-based security assessments, security plans, and levels of security measures (Part A mandatory; Part B guidance). Implementation of ISPS thus connects international obligations with national port governance, private sector operations, and the ship/port interface (IMO, 2004).

Despite the establishment of the International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code as a global maritime security framework since 2004 and its full adoption and implementation in the Nigerian maritime industry in 2007, the Gulf of Guinea (GoG) continues to face persistent maritime security threats that undermine the safety of international shipping and regional economic stability. The region accounts for a disproportionate share of global maritime insecurity, with the International Maritime Bureau (IMB) reporting that between 2010 and 2023, over 45 percent of global piracy incidents occurred in the Nigeria's GoG region (IMB, 2023). While the ISPS Code was designed to strengthen port and ship security through standardized protocols and coordinated government oversight, its practical implementation across West and Central African states remains inconsistent and weakly institutionalized (Agyekum, 2024; IMO, 2023). Thus there seems to remain increasing trend in insecurity in the GoG maritime region.

One core problem is the lack of evidence of to what extent the implementation of the ISPS has been able to achieve a significant reduction or otherwise in the trend and extent of maritime insecurity in the region. There is also an uneven domestication and enforcement of ISPS Code provisions among coastal states in the Gulf of Guinea. Many countries lack adequate legal frameworks, institutional arrangements, and technical capacities to translate the ISPS guidelines into effective port security operations (Mensah, 2022). In several ports, security assessments and certification processes are outdated or inadequately supervised, resulting in operational vulnerabilities that expose port facilities and vessels to organized criminal networks (Onuoha, 2020). Furthermore, the absence of harmonized maritime legislation across regional jurisdictions weakens cooperative enforcement, allowing criminals to exploit jurisdictional loopholes and maritime boundaries (Edeh & Akinola, 2023; Nwokedi, Odumodu, Anyanwu & Dike, 2020).

Another critical challenge lies in the seeming lack of empirical evidence of the quantum of security attacks against ship in the pre-ISPS and post ISPS era as basis for decisions on the implementation outcomes of the ISPS policy. This is worsened by the fragmented maritime security governance structure within the region. Although the Yaoundé Code of Conduct (2013) and subsequent regional initiatives established frameworks for information sharing, joint patrols, and operational coordination among Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) and Economic Community of Central African States (ECCAS), implementation has been slow and uneven. Institutional overlaps, duplication of responsibilities, and bureaucratic inefficiencies have hindered coordinated maritime domain awareness (MDA) and rapid incident response (UNODC, 2022; Nnadi, Nwokedi, Nwokoro, Ndikom, Emeghara and Onyemechi, 2016).

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Moreover, the financial and infrastructural limitations facing many port authorities have constrained full compliance with ISPS standards. Inadequate funding for security infrastructure—such as closed-circuit television (CCTV), access control systems, and perimeter fencing—has left several ports exposed to external threats. Compounding this problem is the limited human resource capacity and poor training of designated security officers responsible for risk assessment and crisis response (Okafor & Mensah, 2021; Ogwo Dike, Nwokedi and Mbachu 2022). These deficiencies not only compromise port security integrity but also discourage foreign shipping lines from engaging in regional trade, thereby affecting the economic competitiveness of Gulf of Guinea ports.

Lastly, governance and corruption-related challenges exacerbate the problem. Weak institutional oversight, political interference in port administration, and lack of accountability has led to mismanagement of maritime security funds and poor enforcement of security protocols (Ausei, 2023). Consequently, while international conventions emphasize preventive security culture and cross-border cooperation, domestic institutions remain reactive and underprepared.

Therefore, the study seeks to address the lack of empirical information on the trend of maritime insecurity in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre and post ISPS eras and the existence of differences in the extent of maritime insecurity in the region in the pre and post ISPS eras as basis for assessing the implementation outcomes of the ISPS policy over the years. There also seems to be ineffectiveness and uneven implementation of the ISPS Code and maritime security governance mechanisms in the GoG, despite the existence of international and regional frameworks aimed at mitigating maritime threats. The persistence of piracy, kidnapping, illegal bunkering, and smuggling indicates that the goals of maritime safety, trade facilitation, and sustainable port operations are yet to be realized. This study aims to systematically analyze the extent and trend of maritime insecurity in the region in the pre and post ISPS Code implementation across key states and ports in Nigeria's GoG region. In line with the aforementioned problems, the aim of the study is to analyze the implementation of International Ship and Port Facility Security Code and maritime security governance in Nigeria's Gulf of Guinea region. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- (i) Evaluate the trend of maritime insecurity faced by ships in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre ISPS era
- (ii) Ascertain the trend of maritime insecurity affecting ship operators in Nigeria's GOG region in the post ISPS era

The research questions addressed in the study are:

- i. What is the trend of maritime insecurity faced by ships in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre ISPS era?
- ii. Is there an increasing trend of maritime insecurity affecting ship operators in Nigeria's GOG region in the post ISPS era?

1.1 Hypotheses

- i. There is no significant increase in the trend of maritime insecurity faced by ships in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre ISPS era
- ii. There is no significantly increasing trend of maritime insecurity affecting ship operators in Nigeria's GOG region in the post ISPS era

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Maritime security governance refers to the institutional frameworks, policies, and mechanisms established to safeguard maritime domains from threats such as piracy, terrorism, smuggling, and illegal fishing (Bueger, 2015). It embodies the collaborative roles of national governments, regional organizations, and international bodies in promoting safety, security, and the rule of law at sea. In the Gulf of Guinea (GoG), maritime security governance involves a network of actors—such as the International Maritime Organization (IMO), regional institutions like the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), and national maritime agencies—working collectively to mitigate transnational maritime crimes (Onuoha, 2019).

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Effective governance mechanisms in this context depend on coordination, information sharing, surveillance, and enforcement capacities. Governance frameworks must integrate policy, legal, and institutional dimensions to ensure coherent and sustainable maritime security outcomes (Bueger & Edmunds, 2017).

The ISPS Code, adopted in 2004 as an amendment to the SOLAS Convention (1974/1988), provides a comprehensive framework for ensuring the security of ships and port facilities against potential threats (IMO, 2023). It establishes responsibilities for governments, shipping companies, and port authorities in identifying and addressing maritime security risks.

The Code operates on two key components:

(i) Part A (Mandatory Requirements): Outlines obligations for contracting governments and shipping entities regarding the implementation of security plans, designation of officers, and threat-level responses.

(ii) Part B (Guidance): Provides recommendations for compliance and effective implementation (IMO, 2023).

In the Gulf of Guinea, the ISPS Code serves as the benchmark for port security management; however, varying levels of implementation, weak institutional capacity, and financial constraints hinder uniform compliance across coastal states (Akinola, 2021).

The Gulf of Guinea is globally recognized as a maritime hotspot plagued by piracy, armed robbery, oil theft, and kidnapping of seafarers (Obi, 2022). These threats stem from governance deficits, poverty, political instability, and inadequate maritime domain awareness. The region's vast coastline—spanning over 6,000 km across more than 17 countries—poses significant challenges for coordinated surveillance and enforcement (Ukeje & Mvomo Ela, 2019). While international and regional initiatives, such as the Yaoundé Code of Conduct (2013), have aimed to strengthen cooperation, inconsistencies in national enforcement and funding gaps have limited their impact (International Maritime Bureau, 2023).

The Gulf of Guinea's maritime governance structure comprises multi-level institutional coordination, including:

- i. International Level: IMO, UNODC, INTERPOL, and EU Navy for support in capacity building and legal harmonization.
- ii. Regional Level: ECOWAS, ECCAS, and GGC implementing frameworks like the Yaoundé Architecture for Maritime Security.
- iii. National Level: Implementation through designated maritime security agencies such as Nigeria's NIMASA, Ghana's Maritime Authority, and Cameroon's Port Authorities. Governance effectiveness depends on how these levels interact, share intelligence, and harmonize responses to maritime threats (Bueger, 2018).

The conceptual framework positions the ISPS Code not only as a technical compliance mechanism but also as a strategic governance instrument for maritime security. By linking implementation outcomes to governance performance, the framework offers a holistic lens for evaluating the Gulf of Guinea's maritime security architecture.

Figure-1: Conceptual Framework. Source: Prepared by the Author.

Framework

There are scanty empirical literature reviews on the implementation outcomes of ISPS code in addressing maritime piracy and insecurity in Nigeria's GoG region. However, Nnadi, *et al.* (2015) analyzed maritime piracy and armed robbery in the Gulf of Guinea region from 2002 to 2015. They used a time-series data of 14 years on the reported piracy and armed robbery attacks in the 15 Gulf of Guinea countries and nine coastal zones of Nigeria. A Trend analysis model and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data. From their findings, it was observed that there was significant variation in piracy and armed robbery attacks among the Gulf of Guinea countries, of which the greatest number of attacks occurred in Nigeria. They also noted that there was also a significant variation in piracy attacks among the coastal zones of Nigeria with attacks in Lagos ports and anchorages being highest within the period under review.

A foundational body of empirical work establishes the Gulf of Guinea (GoG) as a persistent hotspot for piracy, armed robbery, and crew kidnappings. ICC-Commercial Crime Services' reporting based on the International Maritime Bureau (IMB) data documents high incident levels and a pronounced rise in crew kidnappings across the region, particularly during 2019–2023, with notable surges in 2020 and a continued elevated incident count through mid-2023. These industry/monitoring data provide a measured baseline. Several empirical dissertations and case studies examine ISPS implementation in West African ports. Addo's fieldwork on ISPS application at Tema (Ghana) highlights practical gaps between documented security plans and on-the-ground infrastructure and training—for example, inconsistencies in access control, CCTV deployment, and the capacity of designated port facility security officers to perform risk assessments (Addo, 2015).

Etus (2016) used the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Simple regression methodology to model the relationship between Nigeria's economic growth (RGDP) and piracy incidents in Nigerian waterways. Her findings depict that there is an inverse relationship between the two variables such that, RGDP will decrease by 16.8% for every one percent increase in pirates activities in Nigerian waterways. The relationship between the variables is however not statistically significant.

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Okeahalam & Otwombe (2016) used general estimating equations (GEE) modeling to access factors that determine the risk of piracy attacks. They accessed mainly the impact which the level of economic and institutional development in several regions may have on the frequency and success and failure rates of piracy attacks. They found that the frequency of piracy attacks is higher in regions where the quality of institutions is low and that most attacks take place close to a port. Furthermore, their findings depict that successful attacks are most likely in regions that are poor and have low military capacity.

Sascha et al. (2013) studied the contributing factors of maritime piracy by analyzing previous incidents that have been reported to the International Maritime Organization (IMO). Part of the analysis is to filter those ship types that are particularly vulnerable to piracy attacks. The paper also introduces the guidelines developed by the IMO and the industry envisaging minimizing the risk to ships that are exposed to attacks from pirates. It further describes the initiatives taken to develop a sustainable mechanism in the high-risk area (HRA) to suppress piracy and other maritime crimes.

Wong & Yip (2012) used data from ICC International Maritime Bureau (IMB) from 2002 to 2009 with the aid of binary choice models to estimate the success/failure of pirates' attacks as a function of vessel type, flag, vessel operation, number of pirates, boarding methods, and arms type. They used the binary models to quantify how pirates' characteristics and behavior determine the rate of success and degree of violence of pirates attacks. Their results identified three major approaches for pirates' attacks, with the different approaches being associated with different levels of violence, arms used and different targets. It further shows that bulk carriers, general cargo ships, containerships, chemical tankers, and tankers are favorite targets, and these types of vessels account for 76% of all ships attacked from 2002 to 2009.

Jon & Shannon (2014) compared successful and unsuccessful pirates attacks for 4,638 observations against ships worldwide and the situational factors that help prevent such attacks. Their findings show that when a ship's crew takes proactive self-protective measures that increase the perceived effort (increasing speed, employing evasive maneuvers) and increase the perceived risk (embarking private security, having watchman present, raising alarm, increasing lighting, anti-piracy) of perpetrating an attack, unsuccessful attacks are significantly more likely after controlling for environmental influences.

Beloff (2013) noted that Somalis turn to piracy due to poor economic reasons. He further explained that the fall of the Somali government in 1994 marked the advent of piracy in Somali waters. Gries & Redlin (n/a) examined the effects of socio-economic, political, and institutional conditions on maritime piracy for 149 countries between 1991 and 2010 by applying random-effects negative binomial regression. Their results show that, on average, less developed countries with higher political and institutional disorder have a higher probability of piracy attacks. They identified that there exist negative effect of GDP on piracy, suggesting that weak economic development causes piracy, the positive relationship between trade openness and piracy indicates that as trade increases, piracy increases. They also found that dependence on fishery is negatively correlated with piracy, indicating that a decrease in fishery yields results to increase in piracy activities.

Al-Qattan (2016) investigated maritime piracy in the Arabian Gulf and Somalia with a practical objective of understanding the drivers underpinning piracy behavior to aid in identifying how best to deal with the issue. The main findings from empirical data collected using face-to-face semi-structured interviews for 43 observations (undertaken between 2012 & 2013 in Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain, Dubai, Abu Dhabi, Nairobi, and Mombasa) showed that pirates could be categorized according to different strategies adopted in attacking ships: pirates in the Arabian Gulf applied hit and run techniques, while Somalis' pirates adopted a kidnap for ransom approach.

The Yaoundé Code of Conduct (2013) and subsequent Gulf of Guinea Maritime Security Architecture (GoG-MSA) intended to create a regional governance response have been the subject of empirical evaluation. Studies combining policy analysis with interviews of regional officials and operational actors find mixed outcomes: the Yaoundé framework has catalyzed cooperation mechanisms (information-sharing platforms, occasional joint patrols, and training initiatives) but implementation has been uneven due to capacities. A growing empirical literature investigates technology's role—especially MDA systems, coastal radar, AIS data integration, and shared *Evaluation of the Implementation of International Ship and Port Facility Security (ISPS) Code for Maritime Security Governance in Nigeria* Efetobo O. et al (2026) :43-57

information platforms—in reducing incident response times and improving interdiction success. Okafor-Yarwood (2024) synthesizes case studies and quantitative indicators showing that investments in MDA (satellite AIS, shore-based radar, and data fusion centers) are associated with improvements in situational awareness and more coordinated responses. Empirical research documents the growing role of private maritime security companies (PMSCs) and other private actors in the GoG as an adaptation to limited state enforcement capacity. Field interviews, contract analysis, and incident datasets indicate that PMSCs provide immediate deterrence for high-value vessels and can lower boarding rates in their areas of operation. However, researchers warn of mixed long-term effects: PMSCs can create differential protection, complicate legal jurisdiction, and risk. UNODC (2022) and regionally oriented empirical studies examine prosecution rates, legal harmonization, and post-incident follow-through. These works reveal low prosecution and conviction rates for maritime offenses, inconsistent use of national laws to criminalize maritime crime, and logistical hurdles in evidence collection at sea. Consequently, empirical evidence links weak judicial outcomes to low deterrence, fueling repeat offending (UNODC, 2022).

Shane, Piza & Silva (2017) used data from the international maritime bureau to examine which vessels are most at risk of a pirate attack and ransom demand, the relationship between attacks for ransom and violence, which countries experience the most attacks for ransom, the effects of situational crime prevention (SCP) techniques on injuries during attack and the effects of SCP on ransom demands. Their findings show that SCP is a useful strategy for reducing episodes of ransom and injuries, highlighting how SCP techniques can be adapted in unique environments when other traditional crime control resources are unavailable.

Essien and Adongoi (2015) examined Sea Piracy and Security Challenges of Maritime Business Operation in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Research hypotheses were tested using regression analysis. The result showed a significant negative effect of pirate attacks on sea business operations. Hence, adequate security should be provided for sea business operations to facilitate sea business operations in Nigeria. Rami (2010) examined piracy and its impact on the economy with the use of the political economy method. This thesis has shown that piracy has had a large impact not only physically, but financially on society as a whole.

Furthermore, Jiang (2014) examined maritime piracy in Malacca Strait and the South China Sea. He used series hazard modeling and multivariate logistic models to test the relative strengths of deterrence and reactance models for the risk of piracy attacks under a military intervention and several major events. He found significant evidence for the conclusion that the rate of piracy attacks reduced significantly when direct controls are implemented to reduce the environmental opportunities of crime, and when the certainty effect becomes stronger. He further noted that the only exception is when pirates are highly motivated. Also, the results support the reactance perspective when the odds of successful attacks significantly increase after the anti-piracy military intervention was introduced.

Udensi, Etu, and Chieke (2014) examined national security and maritime piracy in Nigeria: A sociological discourse. The discourse used secondary data from International Maritime Bureau (IMB) to show the severity and pattern of piracy in Nigeria waterways, and the tenets of the three capability gap thesis found out that while corruption is the major cause of maritime piracy and insecurity in Nigeria, election malpractices specifically equips the pirates with arms directly or indirectly.

2.1 Research Gap

The study reviewed several studies related to the maritime security and ISPS implementation in Nigeria's GoG region. However, available empirical studies have not been able to:

- (i) Provide empirical information on the trend of maritime insecurity faced by ships in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre ISPS era in comparison to the trend of maritime insecurity affecting ship operators in Nigeria's GOG region in the post ISPS era.
- (ii) Determine the extent of significance of differences in the extent of attacks against shipping industry operators in Nigeria's GoG region in the pre and post ISPS eras

These are the knowledge gaps which this study seeks to address.

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3.0 DATA AND METHODS

The study area of the research is the Nigerian maritime industry with specific concentration on the implementation of ISPS for the purpose of addressing piracy and other maritime security challenges in the Nigerian maritime industry and offshore oil and gas sector. The study area covers the implementation of ISPS policy in addressing security challenges in Nigerian ports of Lagos Apapa port, Tin Can Island, Onne, Port-Harcourt, Warri and Calabar and onboard vessels operating in Nigeria waters and the shipping companies operating in Nigeria. The Nigerian maritime industry and all the coastal zones affected by maritime insecurity constitute the geographical region covered in the study area.

The study used quantitative research design method. This consists of the use of quantitative data sourced from secondary sources. The quantitative research design involve the use of time series secondary data obtained from the International Maritime Bureau (IMB), the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) and Offshore oil and gas industry report. Secondary data on pirate attacks against ships in Nigeria’s maritime sector covering the period from 1993 to 2023 was used for the study.

3.1 Method of Data Analysis

The study employed the use of multiple methods in analyzing the data obtained in line with the objectives of the study. Firstly, it will use the Trend Analysis method to investigate and determine the first, second and fourth objectives of the study which seeks to estimate the trend of maritime insecurity in the Nigerian maritime industry in the pre and post ISPS policy eras. The trend analysis also provided the basic model for extrapolating or forecasting the future trends in pirate attacks against the shipping industry in Nigeria.

The study also used the difference of means statistical method compare pre and post ISPS regime attacks in the shipping industry. Finally, the t-test corresponding to the trend analysis model and the difference of means statistical method were used to test the hypotheses of the study in line with the study objectives.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table1: Descriptive Statistics of Pirate Attacks against Ships in the Pre and Post ISPS Eras

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Pre ISPS piracy</i>	<i>Post ISPS piracy</i>
Mean	15.5	36
Standard Error	2.819574	1.727233
Median	11.5	37
Mode	9	41
Standard Deviation	11.2783	6.908931
Sample Variance	127.2	47.73333
Kurtosis	1.565277	-0.9756
Skewness	1.575432	-0.48932
Range	37	22
Minimum	5	23
Maximum	42	45
Sum	248	576
Count	16	16

Source: Author’s calculation

Table1 above shows the descriptive statistics of pirate attacks against the Nigerian shipping industry in the pre and post ISPS periods. The result shows that an average of 15.5 pirate attacks were recorded per annum between 1992 and 20007 in Nigeria before the implementation of the ISPS policy in Nigeria

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with a standard deviation of 11.28. The aggregate number of pirate attacks against the Nigerian shipping sector in the pre ISPS adoption and implementation era was 248 attacks with a maximum and minimum of 42 and 5 respectively. The range which indicates the difference between the maximum and minimum attack is 37. This indicates that over the period of 16 years from 1992 to 2007 covered in the pre ISPS era, the range of pirate attacks against the shipping industry in Nigeria is depicted by $42 > 37 > 5$.

The result on Table 1 also shows that an average of 36 pirate attacks with a standard deviation of 6.91 occurred in the Nigerian shipping and port sector per annum in the post ISPS era covering the period of 2008 to 2023 covered in the study. An aggregate of 576 pirate attacks occurred against the shipping industry in the 16 years covered in the post ISPS era. The maximum and minimum pirate attacks recorded over the period are 45 and 23 attacks respectively with range of 22. The range which depicts the distribution of attacks against the shipping industry over the period covered in the post ISPS era is $45 > 23 > 22$. The result suggests that greater number of pirate attacks were recorded in the post ISPS era than the pre ISPS suggesting that the implementation of the ISPS policy may not been able to address the challenges of piracy and maritime insecurity in Nigerian maritime sector as a maritime security governance strategy. It underscores that need for the overhauling of the implementation strategy and improving the ISPS governance approaches. The figure 2 below shows the average number of pirate attacks against shipping interests in the pre and post ISPS eras in Nigeria

Source: prepared by the author

Table2: Evaluating the Trend of Maritime Insecurity Faced by Ships in Nigeria’s GoG Region in the Pre ISPS Era

<i>Regression Statistics</i>						
Multiple R		0.681622				
R Square		0.464609				
Adjusted R Square		0.426367				
Standard Error		8.542024				
Observations		16				
<i>ANOVA</i>						
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>	
Regression	1	886.4735	886.4735	12.1491	0.003638	
Residual	14	1021.526	72.96618			
Total	15	1908				
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	1.775	4.479475	0.396252	0.697893	-7.83252	11.38252
X Variable 1	1.614706	0.463256	3.485556	0.003638	0.62112	2.608292

Source: Prepared by the author

Table2 shows the result of the trend analysis carried out to ascertain the trend of pirate attacks against the shipping and ports sector in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era. The result of the study indicates the existence of about 68% positive correlation between the frequency of pirate attacks against the sector in the pre ISPS era and the time (years) of attacks between 1992 and 2007.

The equation showing the trend of pirate attacks against the shipping and port sector in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era is:

$$INSEC_{preisps} = 1.775 + 1.6147X_1 + e \quad (5)$$

This implies that there is an increasing trend in the frequency of pirate attacks in the shipping industry in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era covering the period between 1992 and 2007. The implication is that, for each unit increase in time (per year/ annum) in the pre ISPS era the frequency of pirate attacks against shipping interests in Nigeria increases by an average of 1.6147 attacks. The R-square which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.47 indicating that about 47% variation in the trend of pirate attacks against shipping interests in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era is explained by time (in years) as the explanatory variable.

The t-test indicates a t-score of 3.4856, p-value of 0.0036 and alpha value of 0.05. Since the alpha value of 0.05 greater than the p-value of 0.0036 (0.05 > 0.0036); the study infers that there is a significant increase in the trend of pirate attacks against shipping and port sector interests in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era. Figure3 below shows the linear graph providing more clarity to the trend of pirate attacks against the Nigerian maritime industry in the pre ISPS era.

Figure3: Linear graph showing the trend of maritime piracy in the pre ISPS era in Nigeria. . Source: prepared by the author

Table4: The Trend of Maritime Insecurity Affecting Ship Operators in Nigeria’s GOG Region in the Post ISPS Era

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.127686
R Square	0.016304
Adjusted R Square	-0.05396
Standard Error	7.092886
Observations	16

<i>ANOVA</i>					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	11.67353	11.67353	0.232036	0.637461
Residual	14	704.3265	50.30903		
Total	15	716			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>
Intercept	37.575	3.719541	10.10205	8.24E-08	29.59738	45.55262
X Variable 1	-0.18529	0.384666	-0.4817	0.637461	-1.01032	0.639732

Source: Author’s calculation

Table4 shows the result of the trend analysis carried out to ascertain the trend of pirate attacks(maritime insecurity) against the shipping and ports sector in Nigeria in the post ISPS era. The result of the study indicates the existence of about 13% positive correlation between the frequency of pirate attacks against the sector in the post ISPS era and the time (years) of attacks between 2008 and 2023.

The equation showing the trend of pirate attacks against the shipping and port sector in Nigeria in the post ISPS era is:

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$$INSEC_{postisps} = 37.575 - 0.185X_t + e \quad (6)$$

This implies that there is a decreasing trend in the frequency of pirate attacks in the shipping industry in Nigeria in the post ISPS era covering the period between 2008 and 2023. The implication is that, for each unit increase in time (per year/ annum) in the post ISPS era the frequency of pirate attacks against shipping interests in Nigeria decreases by an average of 0.185 attacks. The R-square which measures the explanatory power of the model is 0.0167 indicating that about 1.7% variation in the trend of pirate attacks against shipping interests in Nigeria in the post ISPS era is explained by time (in years) as the explanatory variable.

The t-test indicates a t-score of -0.4817, p-value of 0.637 and alpha value of 0.05. Since the p-value of 0.637 is greater than the alpha score ($0.637 > 0.05$); the study infers that there is no significant decrease in the trend of pirate attacks against shipping and port sector interests in Nigeria in the post ISPS era. Figure4 below shows the linear graph providing more clarity to the trend of pirate attacks against the Nigerian maritime industry in the post ISPS era.

Figure4.: Linear graph of post ISPS era pirate attacks. Source: prepared by the author

Table5: Compare the Extent of Attacks against Shipping Industry Operators in Nigeria’s GoG Region in the Pre and Post ISPS Eras

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Pre ISPS piracy</i>	<i>Post ISPS piracy</i>
Mean	15.5	36
Variance	127.2	47.73333
Observations	16	16
Pearson Correlation	0.033367	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	15	
t Stat	-6.29405	
P(T<=t) one-tail	7.19E-06	
t Critical one-tail	1.75305	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.44E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.13145	

Source: Prepared by the author

Table5 shows the comparison of the extent of attacks against shipping industry operators in Nigeria’s GoG region in the pre and post ISPS eras. The result shows a mean number of pirate attacks in the pre ISPS era of 15.5 attacks per annum between 1992 and 2007, a period of 16 years covered in the study with a variance on 127.2. It also shows an average of 36 pirate attacks in the post ISPS era per annum over the 16 years with a variance of 47.73.

The difference of means in pirate attacks against shipping and port interests in the pre and post ISPS eras in – 20.5. This implies that more attacks occurred in the post ISPS era than in the pre ISPS era. The t-score of 1.44E-05 and t-critical score of 2.13145 indicates that there is no significant difference in pirate attacks in the pre and post ISPS eras since the t-critical is greater than the t-calculated.

5.0 Conclusion

The study having been able to analyze the implementation of International Ship and Port Facility Security Code and maritime security governance in Nigeria’s Gulf of Guinea concludes in line with the findings of the study that the implementation of the ISPS code has led to reduction in the extent of pirate attacks against the Nigerian shipping industry, though not significantly. There still persists, an increasing trend in the frequency of pirate attacks in the shipping industry in Nigeria in the pre ISPS era covering the period between 1992 and 2007 while there is a decreasing trend in the frequency of pirate attacks against the shipping industry in Nigeria in the post ISPS. The rate of decrease in pirate attacks in the era is however not significant. There is no significant difference in the quantum of pirate attacks in the shipping industry between the pre and post ISPS eras in Nigeria

6.0 Recommendations

In line with the findings of the study, it is recommended that:

- (i) The non-significantly decreasing trend in pirate attacks against shipping interests suggest the need for re-assessing and improving the ISPS implementation strategies in order to achieve a significant reduction/decline in the trend of maritime insecurity affecting both the shipping and offshore oil and gas sectors.
- (ii) The non-significant difference in the quantum of pirate attacks against ships in the pre and post ISPS eras suggest that there is need to improve the ISPS implementation and execution approaches cum maritime security governance approaches in Nigeria’s GoG region in order to achieve significant improvement in the realization of the goals and objectives for the implementation of the policy in Nigeria.

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